

An Adaptive Vehicle Sideslip Estimator for Reliable Estimation in Low and High Excitation Driving^{*}

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Abstract: This work proposes a novel adaptive estimator for reliable vehicle sideslip angle estimation over the full vehicle operating range, using Kalman filtering. It is shown that the vehicle state estimator with adaptive linear tire model proposed in literature only provides reliable estimation for relatively large sideslip angles. This paper proposes a new method that does not suffer this limitation. It relies on the fact that linear tire behavior is mostly a property of the tire/vehicle and to a much lesser extent of the road condition. The proposed estimator therefore contains both a fixed parameter linear tire model, and an adaptive linear tire model. The former allows for reliable and stable estimation for small sideslip angles and linear tire behavior, while the latter allows tracking of nonlinear tire behavior. A smooth transition between the tire models is obtained by adapting the corresponding model covariances in the Kalman filter according to the operating conditions. For this a measure of degree of nonlinearity in tire behavior is defined. Experimental results are provided to demonstrate the robustness and validity of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Sideslip Angle, Adaptive Tire Model, Vehicle Dynamics, Kalman filter, Stability.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades driver assistance systems have become a standard in automotive industry. The performance of these systems could be further improved if more accurate knowledge on the vehicle state, inputs and parameters would be available. However, many of these variables cannot be measured directly in commercial vehicles. Especially for lateral vehicle dynamics control, variables like the vehicle sideslip angle and wheel forces play a crucial role. The direct measurement of these variables requires very costly equipment, respectively an optical speed sensor and force measuring wheels which are not feasible for commercial applications. Therefore, in literature, many model-based estimation approaches employing readily available sensors for these variables have been proposed.

Two main approaches are proposed in literature to develop vehicle state observers. The first approach uses a kinematic vehicle model in combination with measurements from

standard vehicle sensors. Typical measurements are the planar accelerations, yaw rate, wheel speeds and steering angle. The main benefit of kinematics-based estimation is that it is independent from tire parameters and road condition. However, the estimation is sensitive to sensor errors (noise and bias) and unwanted measurements from road grade and bank angle which will cause estimation errors if they are not precisely known. A correction for these errors by GPS measurements is possible, Ryu and Gerdes (2004); Bevely et al. (2006), but the required accuracy is not achievable by consumer-grade GPS and reception may be lost. The second main approach uses a dynamic vehicle model in combination with the measurements from standard vehicle sensors. With this approach the model can correct for sensor inaccuracies and unwanted measurements but information on tire parameters and road condition is needed for the tire model. Many observers have been developed based on this approach, among others by Farrelly and Wellstead (1996); Kiencke and Dai (1997); Doumiati et al. (2010); Boulkroune et al. (2015), where different tire models have been used; the linear tire model, the Dugoff nonlinear tire model, the brush nonlinear tire model, etc. This approach provides stable estimation over the vehicle operating range but considerable estimation bias can occur if the assumed tire model/parameters and/or road condition in the estimator do not correspond to reality, which will often be the case in practice. To be robust to unknown and variable tire/road behavior adap-

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tive tire models have been proposed. In this case, the tire model is formulated such that the unknown tire behavior is estimated simultaneously with the vehicle state by an augmented filter. The most well-known adaptive estimation approaches were developed by Ray (1995), and Best et al. (2000). The approach by Ray considers the entire tire forces as unknown and models their evolution as a random walk model. The approach developed by Best et al. considers the tire forces proportional to the wheel sideslip angle and models the evolution of the proportionality factor (or tire stiffness) as a random walk. This model is referred to as the ‘adaptive linear tire model’. Both approaches have been applied and studied by many authors and the latter was found to perform superior in Naets et al. (2017). Other adaptive estimation approaches have also been proposed in literature; in Grip et al. (2008) a parameter related to road friction is estimated, and in Hashemi et al. (2016) the road friction related term in the tire model is considered as uncertainty. These approaches provide satisfactory results but still require a significant number of tire parameters to be identified related to the linear and nonlinear tire behavior.

This paper starts from an estimator with an adaptive linear tire model as it has been demonstrated to provide good performance with minimal assumptions on the tire/road interaction. However, it is shown that, based on an observability analysis, this approach provides reliable estimation for relatively large sideslip angles only. This limits the applicability of this approach, since the high excitation condition typically only occurs during spirited driving or in emergency maneuvers. This paper proposes a new method that provides reliable estimation over the full vehicle operating range while retaining the general operation of the adaptive linear tire model. It relies on the fact that linear tire behavior at small sideslip angles is mostly a tire/vehicle property and to a much lesser extent dependent on the road condition. The developed estimator therefore combines a fixed parameter linear tire model and the adaptive linear tire model. The former provides reliable estimation in case of small sideslip angles and linear tire behavior, while the latter can account for variable tire behavior (nonlinear tire behavior, road friction changes, etc.) which involves higher sideslip angles. A smooth transition between the tire models is obtained by adapting their respective model covariances in an extended Kalman filter according to the operating conditions. For this a measure of degree of nonlinearity in tire behavior is defined.

This paper is divided into five sections. The second section presents the vehicle state estimator with adaptive linear tire model and explains its limitations based on an observability analysis. Section 3 proposes the new method to obtain reliable estimation over the full vehicle operating range. Experimental results are discussed in Section 4, and Section 5 finally summarizes the findings of this paper.

2. VEHICLE STATE ESTIMATION WITH ADAPTIVE LINEAR TIRE MODEL AND ITS LIMITATIONS

2.1 Model and Measurement Equations

The estimator is based on the bicycle model, as developed by Segel (1956). This model is shown in Fig. 1, where δ

Fig. 1. The bicycle model, as developed by Segel (1956).

is the steering angle, $\dot{\psi}$ the yaw rate, v_x and v_y are the center of gravity (COG) vehicle speeds, β , α_f and α_r the COG, front and rear sideslip angles, F_{xf} and F_{xr} the front and rear per-axle longitudinal tire forces, F_{yf} and F_{yr} the front and rear per-axle lateral tire forces, and l_f and l_r are the distances from the COG to the front and rear axle, respectively.

With this model, and assuming a sufficiently small steering angle, the lateral vehicle dynamics can be formulated as:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{v}_x = a_x + v_y \dot{\psi} \\ \dot{v}_y = \frac{1}{m} (F_{yf} + F_{yr}) - v_x \dot{\psi} \\ \ddot{\psi} = \frac{1}{I_{zz}} (l_f F_{yf} - l_r F_{yr}) \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where a kinematic update equation is added for v_x , and in which a_x is the inertial longitudinal acceleration. This equation transforms v_x into a state variable such that it can be estimated from the available measurements.

These dynamic equations require a tire force model. This work employs the adaptive linear tire model proposed by Best et al. (2000):

$$\begin{cases} F_{yi} = -2C_{yi}\alpha_i \\ \dot{C}_{yi} = 0 \end{cases} \text{ for } i \in \{l, r\}, \quad (2)$$

where C_{yi} is the adaptive tire cornering stiffness, whose evolution is modeled as a random walk to account for variable tire behavior (nonlinear tire behavior, road friction changes, etc.). Substituting tire model (2) in (1) and using kinematic relations for α_i (under a small angle assumption):

$$\alpha_f = \frac{v_y + l_f \dot{\psi}}{v_x} - \delta, \quad \alpha_r = \frac{v_y - l_r \dot{\psi}}{v_x}, \quad (3)$$

results in the following model for the estimator:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{v}_x = a_x + v_y \dot{\psi} \\ \dot{v}_y = \frac{-2(C_{yf} + C_{yr})}{mv_x} v_y - \left(\frac{2(C_{yf}l_f - C_{yr}l_r)}{mv_x} + v_x \right) \dot{\psi} + \frac{2C_{yf}}{m} \delta \\ \ddot{\psi} = \frac{-2(C_{yf}l_f - C_{yr}l_r)}{I_{zz}v_x} v_y - \frac{2(C_{yf}l_f^2 + C_{yr}l_r^2)}{I_{zz}v_x} \dot{\psi} + \frac{2C_{yf}l_f}{I_{zz}} \delta \\ \dot{C}_{yf} = 0 \\ \dot{C}_{yr} = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

with state vector $x = [v_x, v_y, \dot{\psi}, C_{yf}, C_{yr}]$, and input vector $u = [a_x, \delta]$.

The measurement model is:

$$\begin{cases} \psi_{\text{meas}} = \dot{\psi} \\ a_{y \text{ meas}} = \frac{-2(C_{yf} + C_{yr})}{mv_x} v_y - \frac{2(l_f C_{yf} - l_r C_{yr})}{mv_x} \dot{\psi} + \frac{2C_{yf}}{m} \delta, \\ v_{x \text{ best}} = v_x \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

with measurement vector $y = [\dot{\psi}_{\text{meas}}, a_{y\text{meas}}, v_{x\text{best}}]$, where $\dot{\psi}_{\text{meas}}$ and $a_{y\text{meas}}$ are the measured yaw rate and lateral acceleration, respectively, and $v_{x\text{best}}$ is obtained by transforming the measured wheel speeds to the COG and a best wheel selection algorithm.

In this work the extended Kalman filter (EKF) is selected for the joint estimation of vehicle states and tire cornering stiffnesses. The EKF is a straightforward extension of the linear Kalman filter by considering a linearization of the nonlinear system around the current configuration, Simon (2006).

2.2 Observability analysis and limitations

For sequential estimation problems like the Kalman filter, the observability is a key property as it determines whether a state can be estimated with a finite uncertainty. For the extended Kalman filter to be stable a sufficient condition is local observability of the system, Krener (2003). In this work, the Popov-Belevitch-Hautus (PBH) test of observability is applied on the linearized continuous-time system as a proxy for local observability, Ghosh and Rosenthal (1995). This criterion states that a linearized system is locally observable if and only if the matrix:

$$\mathcal{O}_{PBH}(s) = \begin{bmatrix} F - sI \\ H \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

is of full rank for all $s \in \mathbb{C}$, where F is the Jacobian of the continuous-time system (4), and H is the Jacobian of the measurement model (5). As the dynamic model equations are of full rank for all s except for the eigenvalues of the system it is sufficient to check the rank of $\mathcal{O}_{PBH}(s)$ for these eigenvalues λ of system matrix F . For the above described system following remarks can be made based on the PBH-criterion:

- if the sideslip angles α_i are zero, the cornering stiffnesses C_{yi} are unobservable, irrespective of which of the above measurements are used.
- if the sideslip angles α_i are different from zero, at least the yaw rate and the acceleration measurements are required to obtain an observable system.

The first remark indicates that stability issues can occur if the sideslip angles are zero, e.g. during (prolonged) straight driving. In this case there is no information about the lateral dynamics allowing the cornering stiffnesses to have any value while producing the same measurement outputs. This translates into random drift of the cornering stiffnesses. For all other situations ($\alpha_i \neq 0$) the system is locally observable. However, the PBH-criterion provides no information on estimation quality. For this a quantitative measure of observability should be studied. In general it can be said, however, that the estimator will produce highly uncertain estimates if the system is close to unobservable. In this case, the measurements contain only little information about the states resulting in poor estimation. For the current system this occurs in situations with small sideslip angles whereby the cornering stiffnesses are only marginally excited. Unfortunately, this is the most common operating condition of the vehicle.

Fig. 2. Lateral tire force characteristic for different road friction coefficients (curves obtained from a Magic Formula 6.1 tire model with identified parameters).

3. COMBINED ESTIMATOR FOR STABLE OPERATION UNDER LOW EXCITATION

This section presents a combined estimator that provides reliable estimation over the full vehicle operating range. It combines two tire models: a fixed parameter linear tire model, and the adaptive linear tire model. The former is used in case of linear tire behavior (this involves smaller sideslip angles, the regime in which the cornering stiffnesses are only marginally excited and the adaptive linear tire model provides poor estimation), otherwise, the latter is used and can account for variable/nonlinear tire behavior which involves higher sideslip angles. Fig. 2 shows that linear tire behavior is mostly a tire property (and to a lesser extent of the road surface due to changes in the tire contact patch area). As a consequence, a fixed parameter linear tire model can provide accurate estimation in case of linear tire behavior, irrespective of the road condition. It requires only two tire parameters: the front and rear per-axle cornering stiffnesses, \bar{C}_{yf} and \bar{C}_{yr} , respectively.

The proposed estimator is obtained by augmenting measurement model (5) with a virtual sideslip angle measurement that assumes linear tire behavior, β_{lin} . It is obtained by integrating over time the following linear model:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\psi}_{lin} = \frac{-2(\bar{C}_{yf} + \bar{C}_{yr})}{mv_x} v_{ylin} - \left(\frac{2(\bar{C}_{yf}l_f - \bar{C}_{yr}l_r)}{mv_x} + v_x \right) \psi_{lin} + \frac{2\bar{C}_{yf}}{m} \delta \\ \ddot{\psi}_{lin} = \frac{-2(\bar{C}_{yf}l_f - \bar{C}_{yr}l_r)}{I_{zz}v_x} v_{ylin} - \frac{2(\bar{C}_{yf}l_f^2 + \bar{C}_{yr}l_r^2)}{I_{zz}v_x} \psi_{lin} + \frac{2\bar{C}_{yf}l_f}{I_{zz}} \delta \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

with the steering angle and longitudinal speed as input, and small angle assumption $\beta_{lin} = v_{ylin}/v_x$. Note that the per-axle cornering stiffnesses \bar{C}_{yi} , $i \in \{f, r\}$ are assumed to be constant. Several approaches exist to identify \bar{C}_{yi} , see for example Bevely et al. (2006).

For the estimator to work properly, a smooth transition between the linear and adaptive linear tire model is needed according to the tire operating conditions. To this purpose, a measure of degree of nonlinearity in tire behavior is defined, e , and used to adapt the covariance allocated to the linear adaptive model ($Q_{C_{yi}}$) and the virtual sideslip angle measurement ($R_{\beta_{lin}}$). It is calculated as the difference between a predicted yaw rate that assumes linear tire behavior, $\dot{\psi}_{lin}$ and the actual yaw rate, $\dot{\psi}$. The former is obtained from (7), the latter is directly measured.

Fig. 3. Schematic overview of the estimation process.

This results in the following behavior of the combined estimator:

- For nonlinear tire behavior ($\dot{\psi}_{lin} \neq \dot{\psi} \rightarrow |e|$ large):
 - $Q_{C_{yi}}$ are set high. The estimator is properly observable and tracks nonlinear tire behavior by adapting C_{yi} .
 - $R_{\beta_{lin}}$ is set high. The virtual measurement β_{lin} is practically not taken into account because it is not valid for nonlinear tire behavior.
 - For linear tire behavior ($\dot{\psi}_{lin} \approx \dot{\psi} \rightarrow |e|$ small):
 - $Q_{C_{yi}}$ are set low. This prevents the adaptive tire model from tracking noise instead of actual tire behavior.
 - $R_{\beta_{lin}}$ is set low. The virtual measurement β_{lin} accurately predicts the sideslip angle.
- This combination allows for stable and accurate estimation in case the system is close to unobservable.
- No lateral excitation ($\dot{\psi}_{lin} = \dot{\psi} = 0 \rightarrow |e| = 0$):
 - $Q_{C_{yi}}$ are set to zero. This stabilizes the estimator, irrespective of the unobservability. This was proved by Naets et al. (2017).
 - $R_{\beta_{lin}}$ is set low. The predicted sideslip angle is accurate ($\beta_{lin} = 0$).

The obvious benefit of measure $|e|$ is that it is valid for practically any road condition. Indeed, the fixed parameter linear model used to predict $\dot{\psi}_{lin}$ is virtually independent of the road condition. A deviation between the predicted and measured yaw rate thus implies that the tires behave nonlinearly. Figure 3 gives a schematic overview of the estimation process.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The validation tests are performed with the electric vehicle demonstrator of the European Union-funded projects E-VECTOORC (2014), iCOMPOSE (2016), and ITEAM (2017), see Fig. 4 (left). The vehicle is equipped with several sensors: an inertial measurement unit (IMU), sampled at 100 Hz (SBG Systems IG-500A), and a Corrsys Datron S-350 optical sensor to directly measure the sideslip angle (reference). Furthermore, also the integrated Electronic Stability Control (ESC) system sensors are logged: the steering wheel angle and the wheel speeds. The vehicle parameters necessary for evaluating the models and measurement equations are presented in table 1.

4.1 Estimator tuning

The model covariances are chosen as:

Fig. 4. Left: the Range Rover Evoque test vehicle. Right: the test track at the Ford Lommel Proving Ground (LPG).

$$Q_{v_x} = 1 \cdot 10^{-4} \Delta t \text{ (m/s)}^2, \quad Q_{v_y} = 0 \text{ (m/s)}^2, \\ Q_{\dot{\psi}} = 0 \text{ (rad/s)}^2, \quad Q_{C_{yi}} = f_1(|e|) \Delta t \text{ (N/rad)}^2,$$

where Δt is the time step size, and

$$f_1(|e|) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } |e| \leq 0.02 \\ g(|e|) \cdot 500^2, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

in which g is a function that holds the highest value of $|e|$ of the past 1.5 seconds.

The measurement covariance matrix R contains the sensor noise variances:

$$R_{\dot{\psi}} = 2.4 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ (rad/s)}^2, \quad R_{a_y} = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ (m/s}^2\text{)}^2 \\ R_{v_{ij}} = 1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ (m/s)}^2, \quad R_{\beta_{lin}} = h(f_2(|e|)) \text{ (rad)}^2,$$

where

$$f_2(|e|) = \begin{cases} 10^{-8}, & \text{if } |e| \leq 0.02 \\ (g(|e|) \cdot 5)^4, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

and h is a first order low pass filter with a time constant of 0.5 seconds.

Note that these tuning rules cause an abrupt change of covariances for values of $|e|$ around 0.02 rad/s . However, this presents no issue for the estimator.

4.2 Results and Discussion

The proposed estimator is validated experimentally on a challenging handling track at the Ford Lommel Proving Ground (LPG) in Lommel, Belgium, see Fig. 4 (right). Two tests have been performed: a low excitation test (moderate speed), and a high excitation test (high speed).

Low Excitation Test: Fig. 5 summarizes the available measurements: the applied steering angle, the planar accelerations, and the wheel speeds. The yaw rate measurement is shown in the upper plot of Fig. 6 together with its estimate and the yaw rate predicted by linear model (7). The lower plot shows the measure of degree of nonlinearity in tire behavior, $|e|$. Since this test was driven at moderate speed the tires behaved linearly, and model (7) accurately predicted the yaw rate. As a result, functions (8) and (9) assigned a small value to $Q_{C_{yi}}$ and $R_{\beta_{lin}}$, respectively, causing the estimator to primarily

Table 1. Main parameters of the test vehicle.

m	Vehicle mass	2217	kg
I_{zz}	Yaw moment of inertia	3231	kgm ²
l_f	Distance COG - front axle	1.397	m
l_r	Distance COG - rear axle	1.263	m
\bar{C}_{yf}	Front axle cornering stiffness	88500	N/rad
\bar{C}_{yr}	Rear axle cornering stiffness	118200	N/rad

Fig. 5. Measurements for the low excitation test: steering angle, planar accelerations, and wheel speeds.

Fig. 6. Top: measured, linear, and estimated yaw rate. Bottom: measure of degree of tire nonlinearity. Note: the noise on e originates from the yaw rate measurement.

trust the virtual sideslip angle measurement and tempering cornering stiffness adaptation. The resulting sideslip angle estimate is shown in Fig. 7 and compared to the reference measurement and to the result of the original estimator (without virtual sideslip angle measurement and no covariance adaptation, $Q_{C_{yi}} = 500^2 \Delta t (N/rad)^2$). The results show that the proposed approach provides accurate estimation, while the original approach performs poor due to it being close to unobservable (sideslip angles are small). The proposed approach relieves these problems by relying on virtual sideslip angle measurement β_{lin} and by reducing the uncertainty on C_{yi} . Fig. 8 shows the estimated per-axle lateral slip-force characteristics. It shows that the tires behaved mostly linear. The proposed estimator only slightly adapted the cornering stiffnesses.

High Excitation Test: Fig. 9 summarizes the available measurements. The yaw rate is shown in the upper plot of Fig. 10, and the lower plot shows $|e|$, the measure of degree of nonlinearity in tire behavior. Its high value indicates that the tires behaved strongly nonlinear during this test. As a result, functions (8) and (9) assigned a high value to $Q_{C_{yi}}$ and $R_{\beta_{lin}}$, respectively, allowing the adaptive

Fig. 7. Sideslip angle at the COG for the low excitation test: Corrsys Datron reference measurement and estimate by the proposed and original estimator.

Fig. 8. Estimated lateral slip-force characteristic of the front and rear axle for the low excitation test.

Fig. 9. Measurements for the high excitation test: steering angle, planar accelerations, and wheel speeds.

linear tire model to track the nonlinear tire behavior. The estimated sideslip angle is shown in Fig. 11 and compared to the Corrsys Datron reference measurement and to the result of the original estimator. Both estimators provide similar results. This is to be expected as the system is now properly observable and the virtual sideslip angle measurement is practically not taken into account. This proves that the proposed method does not limit the general operation of the adaptive linear tire model. The estimated per-axle lateral slip-force characteristics are shown in Fig. 12. The tires now clearly behaved nonlinear. The estimator successfully adapts the cornering stiffnesses to track this nonlinear behavior.

Fig. 10. Top: measured, linear, and estimated yaw rate. Bottom: measure of degree of tire nonlinearity.

Fig. 11. Sideslip angle at the COG for the high excitation test: Corrsys Datron reference measurement and estimate by the proposed and original estimator.

Fig. 12. Estimated lateral slip-force characteristic of the front and rear axle for the high excitation test.

5. CONCLUSION

This work presented a new method for adaptive vehicle state estimation that provides reliable results over the full vehicle operating range, from low to high lateral excitation. The presented approach uses both a fixed parameter linear tire model, and an adaptive linear tire model together in a Kalman filter. The former model allows for reliable estimation in case of small sideslip angles and linear tire behavior, whereas the latter model accounts for variable tire behavior (saturation, road friction changes, etc.). A smooth transition between the tire models is obtained by adapting their model covariance in the Kalman filter according to the vehicle operating condition. This is achieved by a measure of degree of tire nonlinearity that is defined as the difference between a predicted ‘linear’ yaw rate and the measured yaw rate. The proposed approach is validated experimentally for a low and high excitation test and compared to the vehicle state estimator with adaptive linear tire model proposed in literature. This validation

shows the high reliability of the proposed approach where estimators previously proposed in literature do not generate accurate estimates for the low excitation test. The presented approach is capable of reliable estimation over the full vehicle excitation range with minimum assumptions regarding the tire/road behavior.

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